

New Product Promotion based on Customer Profiling

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September, 2016

Abstract

Targeting customers for a new product that has just been launched in the market has been a difficult task. The main reasons lies in the inadequacy of information regarding the product and the relevant customer behaviour. The use case involved in this study, is a company which aim to target customers based on their responses during a marketing campaign. To address this issue multiple feature extraction techniques had been investigated. The main key components for the feature extraction are the transactional log data and the available open data resources. Moreover, an ensemble supervised learning analysis has been covered in order to asses the features and target the appropriate customers for the new product. After evaluating different models it is shown that the best features are these which involved graph mining procedures to create, then follow the aggregated features and the features principled from the intermittent time series methodology. Furthermore, it is shown that only some exclusive Data Sets are significant in the open data inventory. After the feature evaluation it is suggested the appropriate supervised learning methodology to target the correct customers which turns out to be the regularised gradient boosting. In addition, sampling methodologies are investigated in order to accomplish better estimations over the imbalanced data set.

Keywords – Database Marketing, Big Data, Open Data, Graph Mining, Ensemble Learning

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1 Preface

This dissertation was conducted under the module DS591: MSc Data Science Dissertation of University of Lancaster. The scope of the dissertation was to conduct a research based on the hypotheses of the Data Science team of a UK retail chain company. The main topics covered on this research which conforms with the company's researchers requirements is the usage of Open Data and the practise of Ensemble Classification techniques. The aim of this project is to predict whether a customer will purchase a new product that has just been launched in the market. Some specific details are omitted in this study in order for the procedures to be regarded as reproducible. The results of this project aim to give supportive information to the company's researchers in order to accomplish better predictions. The experiments were implemented using a computer of 16GB and a Virtual Machine of 32GB of memory.

2 Acknowledgements

I would first like to thank my thesis supervisor Professor Angelov Plamen, for his support and his deep understanding and knowledge in Data Mining which helped me formulate the project. I would also like to thank the Company's Data Science team for being responsive and helpful to any queries related to the project.

Moreover, I would like to express my deepest appreciation to the online community for developing my skills and using open source tools.

Finally, I would like to thank my friends, classmates and mainly the academic staff for their support and co-operation during the project.

3 Introduction

3.1 Preliminary Introduction

An issue retail companies face, is to find the particular customers which would be interested for a specific product which has not been launched yet in the market. Hence, Database Marketing techniques are being made of use to provide solution to this problem. A popular Machine learning domain to address this issue is Recommender Systems. Although, existing research recognizes the critical role of Recommender Systems, in some cases typical methodologies would not be applicable. The reason lies in the fact that because the product has not been launched yet (or just being launched) in the market there is no previous (or insufficient) record of it in the transactional database. Marketing approaches, specifically in the CRM (Customer Relationship Management) domain, provide solutions to the described issue by creating customer profiles. Customer profiling involves a broad usage of the customer's data which is not only limited on the customer's purchase transactions. Some examples of these data may include demographic, geographic characteristics or even psycho-graphic characteristics from filling surveys.

Some cross-sectional studies have been found to address the specific problem. It is evident in most of these papers the usage of creating customer profiles. The main methodology derives from using the recorded purchase behaviour of the customers, moreover, in some studies it has been discovered that the usage of Geo-Demographic and Census Data can provide supportive information for understanding customer behaviour and for prediction purposes. These methodologies have been taken into account in this study and formulated for the specific use case. The retail company involved in the project has supplied loyalty cards to its customers. As a result, the purchase behaviour and the customer characteristics have been recorded. The problem stated from the company is which of these customers should be approached for a specific new product. A marketing campaign was initialised and some of the customers replied positively to the new product, hence, the company is willing to get an understanding of the customer behaviour and characteristics in order to be capable of efficiently reaching new customers and inform them about the specific

product.

To address this problem a Supervised Learning methodology was implemented in this study to identify the most likely interested customers for the specific new product. Multiple data sources are collected from the customer's transaction history and their background information. For the former data set a TLOG (Transaction LOG) data is provided from the retail company and for the latter one Open Data resources were used based on the customer's estimate of location of residence.

The shape of the particular research is defined by the usage of multiple data sources from the Open Data inventory and the various feature extraction techniques from the customer's transactional database. Hence, the scope of this study is to provide innovative feature extraction techniques and data mining methodologies to address the issue of customer selection on an unreleased retail product. Ethical considerations could be argued on using and manipulating customer's details. In particular the manipulation of the exact customer's information would confront with the latest Data Protection Act. Therefore, to conform with the privacy regulations, part of the customer's postcode address was removed before being handled to the particular study. As a result, stated from [2] these laws have a positive effect from a qualitative point of view, however, they are likely to reduce the amount of direct mail sent to customers for promotion purposes.

3.2 Outline

The body structure of this study starts with the Background. In that chapter to better understand the problem formulation the Marketing theory concepts are investigated. Following are covered the Related Studies which demonstrate a variety of approaches in Market targeting. Finally, the Background chapter provides the literature review and critical conceptual analysis that formulate the Feature Extraction methodology. After the Background chapter the company's Data is presented and analysed. Next, proceeds the Feature Extraction methodology then the Supervised Learning methodology with the outcomes, which are Analysed in the last chapter of the Discussion and Conclusion.

4 Background

4.1 Theoretical Background

Central to the entire discipline of Customer Profiles is the concept of the CRM domain. “CRM refers to the principles, practices and guidelines that an organization follows when interacting with its customers. From the organization’s point of view, this entire relationship encompasses direct interactions with customers, such as sales and service-related processes, and forecasting and analysis of customer trends and behaviors. Ultimately, CRM serves to enhance the customer’s overall experience” [3]. The subcategory of the CRM which is focused in the particular study is Database Marketing. Database Marketing is an approach using customer database to communicate directly with customers and monitor the building of customer relationships and sales [2]. The advantage of the Database Marketing (DBM) in comparison with other types of Marketing as stated by Merlin Stone et al. (1987) [4] is that DBM has the ability to anticipate customer needs better since it intensifies a dialogue with them at the right time and provide the appropriate product or service. It also enables a company to identify groups of its own customers whose needs are served less well. Identifying them in time and supplying products or services to meet their needs reduces the risk of competitive inroads.

According to Marianne Seller et al. (1999) [5] survey there are many types of DBM. Companies discussed in the survey state to have different kind of DBM based on the company’s background. Some of them are: Targeted Marketing (Targets catalogs to specific audiences based on data about group interests), Predictive marketing (Keep existing customers by finding those likely to depart and making them special offers), Loyalty programs (Recording habits by using a card provided to the customer) and Friends and Families (Phone users given discounts when calling friends). In this case study the interest is focused on Targeted Marketing. This can be better described as using statistical analysis or Data Mining techniques of customer attributes and characteristics to determine specific audience for each promotion. In the pages that follow, the focus remains on targeting customers for a specific product which has just been launched in the market.

4.2 Related Studies

A considerable amount of literature have been published exposing DBM techniques and methodologies. However, the procedures discussed vary and do not converge to a specific methodology. Specifically, for the Targeted Marketing DBM appear a variety of concepts and implementations. To begin with, depending on the available Data, studies have shown to use Unsupervised and/or Supervised Learning to target the appropriate customers. For instance a study [6] using Demographics Data and some domain additional data resources propose to use SOM (Self Organizing Maps) and k-means Clustering techniques to segregate the Customers and then sponsor them with offers based on each cluster's RFM (RecencyFrequencyMonetary) [7] rank. Another study [8] which also favors the Unsupervised methodology, suggests clustering by using a modified similarity metric which takes into account the aggregated measures of a customer's Items Variety and her money spent, documented on a retail Data Set. Moreover, it proposes enhancing the clusters quality by using a GA (Genetic Algorithm) on the customer's attributes. Ultimately, it uses the same RFM measure to rank the clusters. Using the described methodologies would explain a considerable amount of the customer behaviour, however, in this paper's use case it makes also sense to review the Supervised Learning methodologies since the company sponsoring the study has provided a binary variable determining if a Customer bought the product of interest or not during a marketing campaign.

The Supervised learning methodologies for Targeted Marketing vary accordingly. Firstly, it can be distinguished in this study [9] the usage of Ensemble Learning methodologies (Boosting [10]) with ANN (Artificial Neural Networks) and logistic regression via SAS (Data Mining Software) which provides estimates from a Telecommunication's Data Set; moreover the additional Demographic attributes on the customers indicate which of them will churn or not. Following, another study [11] focuses also on using ANN but uses an embeded implementation of GA for the attribute selection on the features of an Insurance Data Set. Finally, in the study [12] can be noticed the usage of SLIQ [13] a tree component classifier predicting the prospective customers of a prodcut. In addition, the SLIQ implementation provides clusters of the customers used in that case study, where the Data Set is populated with Geo-demographics and Demographic characteristic of the customers.

Conclusively, it is shown that different approaches have been implemented to Target Customers, some of them using Supervised Learning while others using Unsupervised Learning and yet some use both. In addition it can be noticed in few examples the usage of the Customer behaviour and the usage of his/her Geo-demographic and Demographic characteristics.

4.3 Focal Theory

The focus of this paper is to use Supervised Learning and predict which customers will buy the product of interest. Much weight has been given in the feature extraction techniques. The main source of the Data used for the Supervised Learning is the TLOG, the customer's purchase transaction log and the Open Data, the (Geo) Demographics which are identified by the Customer's Postcode. In the following sections are argued different approaches from the literature and is established a pathway for the Feature Extraction methodology section which would suit with the specifications of the particular case case.

4.3.1 TLOG

Unarguably the TLOG Data has a pivotal role in the extraction of the customer's information. Although the TLOG Data can provide an abundance of information, it is challenging to model this kind of data. Especially, if we take into consideration the large cardinality of customers and products resulting into many combinations. Thus, Transaction mining has been a particular concern over numerous studies and competitions ¹. Subsequently, the main issue when dealing with this kind of data is to what extent calculation of TLOG feature extraction should be applied and what kind. Since can be sourced from simple calculations to some very computational expensive algorithms.

4.3.1.1 Recommender Systems The most prominent domain of Machine Learning which uses TLOG data are the Recommender Systems. Their scope is to by applying a set of procedures distinguish which item(s) are the most suitable for a customer, hence it could be proposed to him/her and build a better Customer Rela-

¹Kaggle Competition example (1), Kaggle Competition example (2)

tionship. The Recommender Systems can be divided into two main disciplines [14]: Content Based and Collaborative filtering. A Content Based Recommender Engine would imply the usage of the technique TF-IDF [15] to attach labels on Customers and/or Items in this case study and through a Vector Space Model procedure set estimates of likelihood to a new product concerning each customer. This implementation would be possible in this case study since the use case company has labeled each Product in hierarchies. Moreover, in this case study it would be suitable to make use of this procedure since it does not require prior information about the product; which fits in this study as the product of interest has just been launched and the likelihood by the Customers is not sufficiently measured. However, the sample of the Customer's provided is a targeted sample, and it was shown that the customer's of the sample behave mostly similarly are interested in the same product categories more or less. Henceforth, the Content Based approach was deprecated.

The Collaborative Filtering approach, resides in the ideology of extracting information from the Users/Customers directly. The use cases are noticeably mostly in the Rating Systems domain, for instance Online Movie Ratings Databases [16]. In this category the state of the art algorithms [14] are regarded to be the Matrix Factorization Models. However, these models have to be modified to be applicable in the retail industry. A case study [17] shows how the SVD (Singular Value Decomposition) approach was used to predict the number of sales of each tuple Customer \times Item for each month. Moreover, in that study for accuracy reasons the Customers were Clustered prior to the SVD implementation. However, in this case study there is not sufficient documentation of the product. Furthermore, even if from priori knowledge was known which products act similarly with the product of interest there are still complications with this methodology. The first one, has to do with the big expense in computational power, secondly, the distribution of the Products should be approximately follow a normal distribution [17] which do not comply with the Data Set of this use case and lastly, to set a monthly interval possibly would not fit with the seasonality component of the specific product cause is not of a daily product category.

Another methodology used in Collaborative Filtering Recommender Systems [14] and beyond is the Graph approach. The notion behind the Graph approach

is the Graph construction where each instance in the TLOG data is documented in the Graph. A typical approach is using a Bipartite Graph and populate the nodes in the Graph with the Customers and the Products and then establish links and attributes based on the TLOG data. Then algorithms are applied to compute the Average first-passage/commute time of node (Customer in this case study). The average first-passage time is the average number of steps needed by a random walker to reach a node j for the first time, when starting from a node $i \neq j$. For instance in this research [18] the average commute time was to compute the distance between the nodes of a bipartite graph where the two groups were the users and the items in a recommender system. The average commute times can be used in two different ways: 1) recommending to a customer the item i for which $n(u, i)$ is the smallest, or 2) finding the nearest customers to the one of interest, according to the commute time distance, and then suggest to this customer the item most liked by the nearest customers [14]. The methodology of the 1 point was detailed investigated in this study in order to provide to each Customer an estimate of her probability of purchasing the product of interest.

4.3.1.2 Time Series Covering the TLOG mining from another perspective in the domain of predictors are Time Series. The idea resides in forecasting the future buying pattern based on the already documented buying pattern of the Customers. The straightforward approach in this case study would be to forecast the purchase of the customers based on the product of interest, however, as mentioned there is very little documentation of the product since it was just launched. Hence, one possible solution would be to speculate when the customer will buy the product based on the forecast of when the customer will go to shop. Although this methodology might provide some valuable information albeit, it is not sure if the customer in her visit will buy the product of interest. Subsequently, one can argue that the usage of Multivariate Time Series could be an option. The reason lies in the hypothesis that the purchase time series of similar products might have similar time series accordingly. Thus by using Multivariate Time Series were the input could be the time series of all the similar products to the product of interest, might produce a reasonable guess of when the customer will buy the product of interest. However, in this case study it was provided which products belong in the same category, hence,

the step taken was to take measurements on when a customer will be more likely to purchase the product of interest based on the inputs on when she buys the products of the same category. Consequently, this was the approach covered in the following pages plus the measurement of the usual buying patterns of the customers.

4.3.2 Open Data

The Open Data is the other part of the Feature Extraction procedures which is based on the Customer Profiling theory (see subsection 4.1). The pointers that suggested on which attributes to retrieve for the Customer Profiling were provided by [19]. In that research it is proposed to retrieve features of the customers as following:

- Geographic
- Cultural and ethnic
- Age
- Values, attitudes, beliefs
- Life cycle
- Knowledge and awareness
- Lifestyle

Taking into account these Customer properties an effort was given to attribute each of these bullet-points in this research. Hence, in the Open Data analysis covered later the retrieved attributes specify each customer's approximate location, cultural background; moreover the usage of Internet as the knowledge and awareness claim, then the type of dwellings that they live, the car availability, the living arrangements and the average distance to the shop are regarded to conform with the Lifestyle and the Life cycle that the customer have. In addition it is estimated the economic activity and occupation that each customer have. Moreover, some of these estimations are focused on the gender specific since as discussed later these customers populate the significant part of the potential buyers for the product. Lastly, the Age was provided by the company's Data Sets.

5 Data Presentation

The company had provided for this project 5 Data Sets, with the expectation of accomplishing Supervised Learning based on the last Data Set (Responses). Recapitulating the company's objective, is to predict which customer's will buy a specific product which had been just launched on the market. Specifically, there is a Transactional Data Set (TLOG Data) provided, which has records from 2013-12-01 to 2016-01-31 (yyyy-mm-dd) inclusively. Moreover, the product of interest was launched on 2016-01-02; following the marketing campaign of the product took place between 2016-02-19 to 2016-03-30 inclusively. Finally, the binary responses (used for the Supervised Learning) of the customers who bought or not the specific product were on the same dates as of the campaign's. Conclusively, we have the TLOG Data, the Customer's description along with the descriptive Data Sets about the products and the stores; accompanied with the binary responses.

Data TimeLine

Figure 1: The time line represents the Data and the entities involved in this project. The graph was made using d3.js [1].

Prior heading into the exploratory analysis of the Data Sets, a valid point should be established on the sample of the customers. In this particular study a targeted sample of customers was provided based on their transactional log. The company's intelligence targeted customers which already bought similar products in their purchase history or had bought other products for the similar purpose/use. The sample makes up to 70K instances from which only 2% are positive (i.e. bought the product of interest on the campaign's dates). The Data Sets have as following: Customers Data, Stores Data, Product Data, TLOG Data and the Responses. (figure 2)

Figure 2: Entity diagram of the Data Sets. In bold are the ID attributes representing how all these Data Sets can be joined. More explicit information about the attributes can be found on the Appendix subsection 9.1.

The occurrences of the customers, products and stores were counted and can be viewed on the Appendix subsection 9.2. It is remarkably noticed that the occurrences are highly skewed for each one of the three entities.

6 Feature Extraction Methodology

6.1 Introduction

This section is divided into three conceptual Feature Engineering methodologies. The first is the feature extraction based on the Data sets provided by the company. Next, is the Open Data merging based on the customer’s approximate location. Finally, the two former approaches are combined to produce some additional features. Great effort has been given into the exploitation of the TLOG data. Moreover, Open Data munging with the customer attributes has been investigated thoroughly to find possible patterns (Data Snooping). On figure 3. can be seen the the entire

feature Engineering pipeline - scheme for this project were on the right is the end result (Tabular Data) from where the Supervised Analysis took place.

Figure 3: Feature Engineering pipeline (In blue is represented the Data provided by the company whereas in Green is the Open Data. The arrows represent the joins and the transformations of each Data Set, color and widths of the arrows are only for visual purposes.)

6.2 Feature extraction on company's Data

In the first part of the feature extraction methodology it was of a vital importance to analyse and exclude possible customers with corrupt information or being too unresponsive in their purchase history. Next, over the following subsections will be

analysed each feature extraction based on figure 3.

6.2.1 Hard Rules - Outliers

Most of the part of the Data Sets had no missing values or extreme values. As expected only the Customer Data Set was not flawless. Some instances of Age where extreme or missing and some Postcodes where irrelevant with the UK Postal codes. Below, can be seen the summary statistics of Age and Gender, however the Postcodes will be analysed on the Open Data chapter where the Postal Codes get validated with look-up tables.

```
summary(Customers$"GENDER")
```

##	F	M	U
##	69886	78	36

```
summary(Positive.Customers$"GENDER")
```

##	F	M	U
##	1378	2	0

```
summary(Customers$"AGE")
```

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	NA's
##	16.18	26.35	32.94	33.69	40.65	104.10	331

```
summary(Positive.Customers$"AGE")
```

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	NA's
##	17.98	25.78	31.94	33.14	40.01	80.74	6

```
summary(Negative.Customers$"AGE")
```

##	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.	NA's
##	16.18	26.37	32.97	33.70	40.66	104.10	325

As can be seen there are now significant measures between the positive and the negative customers, the gender favors the female gender and the age remains approximately the same:

```
boxplot(Negative.Customers$"AGE",Positive.Customers$"AGE")
```


Hence there is not enough proof of evidence to neglect this information, as it might provide information value when combined with other features in latter stages.

Moreover, from the TLOG data were discovered four logical applicable rules to reduce the Negative Customers with no loss of information. This was applied in order to balance the Data Set and to make better predictions. However it did not balance the Customers between the Positive and the Negative as it were removed only a few instances since the Customers as stated were already targeted from the company's intelligence. Hence the ratio Positive to all customers remained 2%. Nevertheless, below can be seen which approaches were taken upon respecting a 10% interval to accept possible marginal new customer behaviour.

1. Disregard Customers with no product purchases of the specific product same hierarchy (Item Hierarchy Description_5, join with TLOG see figure 2)
2. Disregard Customers with low purchases the last year (i.e. less than 4) can be removed with no loss.
3. Disregard Customers with abnormal sales in the last year (i.e. more than 400 number of sales)

4. Disregard Customers who are considered cold. It was found that customers who had made no purchase more than 123 days were unlikely to appear in the Positive Customer section. Thus respecting the 10% interval, the customers who had made their last purchase in the TLOG data before 145 days were removed.

6.2.2 Feature Extraction

6.2.2.1 Aggregated Metrics Regarding TLOG data the most prominent attribute to take into account are the aggregated measures i.e. "How many times did a customer visit the company's shops? or "What is the aggregated amount spent on her purchases?". Hence, the first metrics taken were the Aggregated metrics. These result into two basic features the aggregated amount spent by a customer and the amount rewarded for each customer. These measures were taken from all the period time of the Transactional Data. Finally they were scaled using Z-standardization and inserted into the tabular Data.

6.2.2.2 Intermittent Time Series Apart from these measures, a metric was needed to describe the Customer's frequency of visiting the company's stores. However, attributing each customer with her own specific time series of purchases result into major sparse data. Therefore intermittent Time Series approaches were investigated in this research. The tool used to model the intermittent time series was produced and maintained by Nikolaos Kourentzes (2016) [20].

The most popular method to model intermittent time series is to use Croston's method which proposes a method based on separate exponential smoothing which estimates the demand size and the interval between demands, however research has indicated that that methodology suffers from bias. In detail it has been highlighted that Croston's method suffers from a bias in comparison to other methods used for intermittent time series Teunter (2009) [21]. Hence, the to fill the literature gap numerous efforts have been made [22] [21] [23]. In this particular study was chosen the approach by Gwern (2014) [24] which acknowledges the lack of consistency over the conventional metrics and proposes new metrics which describe succinctly the type of intermittent time series. As declared earlier the package [20] was used to

describe measures of the average inter-demand interval, the squared coefficient of variation and the trend of the customers purchase history.

Getting Technical: The first step was to create extract each customer’s specific purchases Dates and the amounts from the TLOG Data and transform them into intermittent time series. This was carried out using the R packages `data.table` [25] and `dplyr` [26]. After the transformation had been done the intermittent time series [20] was used to extract the Coefficient of variation squared of non-zero demand which can be represented as :

$$v = \sum_1^n \left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\mu_i} \right)^2$$

where i refers to only non zero instances in the time series, σ is the standard deviation and μ is the mean. Following the inter-demand interval was measured which can also be described as: $p = \sum_1^j \mu_j$, where j are the intervals expressed as lengths between the customer’s purchases. Moreover, from the Customer’s purchases a trend value was extracted using a linear regression. However, to be able to fit a linear regression on the intermittent time series of each customer, a step had to be taken of decomposing the time series by taking into account only the positive values/demands. Finally, the outcomes were scaled and merged with the Tabular Data.

In addition, this methodology of using intermittent time series was tested into considering only Customer purchases which entailed similar items with the one of interest using the item hierarchy description attribute (see figure 2). However, this method was deprecated due to the big sparsity in the intermittent time series when on the TLOG data was extracted for each customer only the specific products.

6.2.2.3 Customer relationship to particular products According to the Focal theory bipartite graphs were fitted into transactional Data to extract knowledge and features. Hence, this approach was also embedded in this study in order to uncover possible relationships between customers, between products and between customers and products. The specific topic of feature extraction via Bipartite Graph is covered into two sections: Graph Architecture and Graph Mining.

Graph Architecture: This topic covers the implementation and the gradual improvement of creating a bipartite graph between customers and products in order

to extract possible features for the Customers which will be beneficial for the Supervised Learning, covered in the latter chapters. To begin with, a bipartite graph is type of graph where node entities are divided into two distinct categories, in our case customers and products. Moreover, the main difference of the rest graph implementations is that in a bipartite graph a node can be linked only with a node of the other group. To view the formulation of this rule the figure 4 depicts a Bipartite Graph on the current TLOG Data Set where the red nodes are the customers and the blue nodes are the products.

Figure 4: A Bipartite Graph small sample of 10 Customer’s of the provided Data Set with the first purchases they made in the TLOG Data. The red nodes represent the customers and the blue the products.

The Graph formulation and visualization was done using the Networkx module via Python [27]. The rest graph implementations discussed were produced accordingly.

Moreover, a link/edge rule had to be established in the graph implementation, since there are four main approaches that can be done implemented. The first one is to allow each node to be connected with another node only once (Graph), the second is to allow multiple connections/edges between nodes (Multigraph), the third is to use the first approach but giving a direction to the edge (DiGraph) and the fourth approach is to use multiple directed edges between nodes (DiMultiGraph). In this

study the first approach was used.

Continuing, in a graph implementation, attributes can be set on the nodes and on the edges as well. A remark should be settled in this stage, that no attributes were given on the customer's nodes since on the tabular Data the rest of the features are features of the customers. However, attributes to the Product nodes were given but will be described later. The Edges, were assigned with one attribute, the frequency (i.e. how many times) a customer bought the product. Furthermore, efforts were given to attach more attributes to the edges like the last time a customer bought the specific product which she is linked to, or if she used any discount. Notwithstanding the information gain of attaching these attributes would have been, it was preferred to keep the Graph implementation with one edge attribute/weight due to the fact that customizable approaches for Link Prediction (covered later) should have been used, apart from that the other features of the tabular data aim to cover these characteristics from a different perspective.

Figure 5: A Bipartite Graph with a bigger sample of customers and their purchases from the provided TLOG data, where colored edges infer more than one purchase. The red nodes represent the customers and the blue the products.

At the first stage, a Bipartite Graph was carried out with all the customers and products. By doing that, it limited the offered resources for the study. Hence,

new approaches were investigated. Different experimental designs took place, like limiting the TLOG Data by taking into account only the last year of the TLOG Data or taking into account only the products that belong to the same category (Item Hierarchy Description figure 2) as this of the product of interest. Furthermore, parallel graph implementations were put under the microscope. Either by providing ready based distributed solutions, with some of the latest API graph technologies like GraphFrames [28] or GraphX [29] (more researches on the topic of Bipartite Graph distributed systems are covered by Rong Chen et.al (2014) [30] and API Yucheng Low (2012) [31] where is used the GraphLab API) or distribute the Graph on customer communities. The latter option would include distributing the Bipartite Graph either by grouping customers who have similar purchases or distribute the Graph by limiting each Graph with all the Customers but providing a sub-sample of the products to each Graph.

Ultimately, the solution was to collect and populate the Bipartite Graph with products that were of a particular interest and using only the 7 latest months Data of the TLOG Data. This approach was chosen to balance the resources and the information gain that the Graph could possibly provide. The specified solution involves of populating the Graph with only products that are remarkably different in consumption between the Positive and the Negative Customers; thus its name Supervised high n low ratio products (figure 3). The selection of the products was made by measuring the appearances of each product between the separate groups (i.e. Positive and Negative Customers) using the plyr library [32]. Subsequently, by dividing the appearances from the Positive group to the Negative group a ratio was produced. This ratio was then ordered on an ascending manner, having on top the more favorable items of the Positive Group ² and on the bottom the least favorable items. Moreover, because this methodology was carried out with all of the customer's data, in order not to be biased of picking the items which possibly might not had been discovered by taking into account a sample of the Data (training Data), a threshold was established to eliminate the bias. This threshold was given a generous measure of up to 1K appearances in the Negative Group which translates into much more than 20 occurrences in the Positive group ³. Then from the sorted

²I.e. > 2% the percentage of the Positive Customers on the provided sample.

³Regarding the 2% Positive/All Customers in the unbalanced Data Set.

list of products two Bipartite Graphs were generated, one with the top 10% of the products and the second the low 10% of the products. Lastly, in both of the graphs the product nodes were assigned with the attribute of the Ratio they had in the predefined sorted list.

Graph Mining: This topic covers the Graph Mining part of the two produced Graphs, meaning the feature extraction from the Graphs that then were fitted in the tabular Data Set. In Graph Mining exist a variety of algorithms which can be used to extract information from it. In this paper because the edges/links between products and customers are of interest, this is why the algorithms were narrowed upon two categories Link Analysis and Link Prediction. The Link prediction algorithms refer to the prediction of a node in a graph attaching to another node whereas Link Analysis algorithms aim to provide information about the graph by considering the current state of the edges in the graph. This part of the Graph Mining approach is covered into two sections the Link Prediction and Link Analysis, where the latter one was used to extract features from the Graph for the particular study.

Link Prediction is the estimate of a new link being created. This approach can be illustrated clearly when viewing the paper of Mohammad Al Hasan et.al (2006) [33] where two graphs where generated from some Bibliographic Databases. The nodes from these graphs represented the papers of these Databases and the edges where drawn when papers had the same co-authors (Graph implementation). Consequently, the features of each paper where extracted like the keyword match count, sum of papers by the author of the paper, the sum of keyword count, sum of neighboring nodes e.t.c. and then using Supervised Learning on a training Set (drawn edges) it could be predicted which nodes (papers) would connect on the test set (un-drawn edges). The same principle consists the rest of the Link Prediction techniques where some information of the graph is extracted in order to view the probability of a node being attached to another node.

Moreover, there some implementations [34] [35] [36] focusing Link Prediction methodologies specifically on the bipartite graphs to address the issues of the different group of nodes. Because, the challenge in the bipartite graphs is that many metrics which use neighboring methodologies are not applicable because the only neighbors a node has is of the other group of nodes and not of its own group. How-

ever, in the current study use case where the approach was to extract features from the Graph and assign them to the tabular Data, Link Prediction methodology was not a favorable approach. The reason lies in the fact that Link Prediction output would produce a Similarity matrix between the customers. The only solution to extrapolate the usability of this matrix would be to produce a set of features by using multi-dimensional-scaling (MDS) ⁴ and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) ⁵ and then the created vectors should be attached into the tabular Data. This might not have been an erroneous approach however using MDS indicates a loss of information, thus the study's direction was pointed at the usage of Link Analysis algorithms instead.

The Link Analysis algorithms aim at the assignment of a given rank to each node in the graph based on their activity in the graph. Hence, for this study, attributing a given value to each customer for the further Supervised Learning purpose seemed a plausible approach. To review the Link Analysis from a broader perspective, one should firstly take into account simple metrics that provide node with information, like the node degree which refers to the edges a node has. Thus a node with a higher node degree, a customer in this study, would imply that this customer is more probable to be a Positive or a Negative Customer depending on the graph architecture described above. Undeniably, there exist many metrics in the literature that characterize nodes, however, in this study were reviewed some of the most popular and applicable to the Bipartite Graph study case.

The first measurement that was considered was the closeness centrality [37]. This metric was regarded adequate for the Bipartite Graph Link Analysis study, since it measures the paths from a node to all the other nodes. Hence, in the specific case study it will rank higher the customers who are more connected to the products. In specific, the closeness centrality measurement involves the sum of the shortest path

⁴An MDS algorithm aims to place each object in N-dimensional space such that the between-object distances are preserved as well as possible. Each object is then assigned coordinates in each of the N dimensions (Multidimensional scaling - wikipedia.org).

⁵Principal component analysis (PCA) is a statistical procedure that uses an orthogonal transformation to convert a set of observations of possibly correlated variables into a set of values of linearly uncorrelated variables called principal components (Principal component analysis - wikipedia.org). In addition, the PCA will be covered later in more depth.

distances from a node u to all other nodes $n - 1$. The equation can be written as:

$$C(u) = \frac{n - 1}{\sum_{u=1}^{n-1} d(v, u)} \quad (1)$$

where the $d(v, u)$ is the shortest path distance between the node u and v . Moreover, since the sum of distances depends on the number of nodes in the graph, closeness centrality is normalized by the sum of minimum possible distances $n - 1$.

Although, this algorithm would produce some scores/ranks for the Customers, a similar promising technique was to consider Closeness Vitality [38]. This technique encapsulates the same idea, however, when the Closeness Vitality score is produced for a node, the sum of distances between all node pairs are considered when excluding that node. Moreover, as an enhancement for the return scores of these algorithms is to consider the frequency of a customer buying a product. This implementation would require the usage of Dijkstra algorithm ⁶ to compute the distance between node u and v and including the weight assignment. However, the above two approaches Closeness Centrality and Closeness Vitality were considered deprecated because of the incapability of embedding the node information, the product ratio as described in the Graph Architecture. Thus, new algorithms had to be investigated.

The solution to fill the gap of embedding the product ratio attribute was given by the algorithm Pagerank and in particular the Personalised Pagerank algorithm [40] [41]. The Pagerank algorithm used to implement was provided by the NetworkX module [27]. Below, on the Algorithm 1 can be viewed the part of the code which was used to calculate the Customers rank. The data structure which defines each Customer with his rank is named x , which is also the output of the code. The W Data Structure represent a copy of the Graph where for each node, the sum of the weights of all the edges of that node is 1 and the weight of the edges are taken into account. The alpha parameter represents the Damping factor which was left as default 0.85. Finally, the Personalise data Structure is the structure which links each Product with the assigned ratio found described on the Graph Architecture and Customers were assigned with an insignificant score of 0.1.

⁶A dynamic Programming approach to compute the shortest path between a node u and v [39].

Algorithm 1 Personalised Pagerank

```
1: for counter = 1 to 100 do                                ▷ the defined iterations for convergence.
2:   xlast = x
3:   x = new()                                                ▷ Initialise x
4:   for all u in x do                                       ▷ u is the node being processed
5:     ▷ u can be regarded as the Customer node and v the Product nodes.
6:     for all v in W[u] do                                    ▷ v are the neighboring nodes
7:       x[v] = x[v] + alpha * xlast[u] * W[edge(u,v)][freq]
8:     ▷ freq is the number of purchases of the product v.
9:   x[u] = x[u] + (1.0 - alpha) * Personalise[u]
```

The actual *NetworkX* algorithm⁷ differs from this pseudocode, since there are no Dangling nodes⁸ in this case study because it involves a non-directed Graph. Where a transformation had to be done from a non-directed Graph to an directed Graph by setting each edge into an ingoing and outgoing edge.

The Personalized Pagerank algorithm was executed two times, one for each of the generated graphs and the two outputs was were scaled and inserted into the final Tabular Data.

6.2.2.4 Shop Prediction A useful aspect that would contribute on the Supervised Analysis is whether the customers will go and shop during the campaign period (see section 5). The reason lies in the fact that the time interval of the campaign period were the responses were recorded (see figure 2) may be not large enough to include some customer's visits at the shops. Thus, these potential customers might had been interested in buying the product of interest but had the opportunity to buy it, right after the campaign period. Hence, the methodology of this feature extraction takes firstly into consideration the last visit the customers had in a shop. Subsequently, for each customer were calculated the interval of shopping the product in the same category as the product of interest (see table 8 at attribute Hierarchy Description 6). This calculation was done with the same methodology applied in paragraph 6.2.2.2 using the packages [20], [25]. Following, the probability of shop-

⁷Can be viewed on [networkx.github.io](https://github.com/networkx/networkx).

⁸Dangling nodes are the ones which have no outgoing edges.

ping in the exact time interval of the campaign (see figure 1) was calculated, scaled and fitted in the tabular Data.

6.2.2.5 Type n Capacity of stores visited The retail company which sponsored this research has different kind of shops. These shops differ between on the products, the services provided and the size of each store. The attribute providing this information can be found on the Appendix chapter table 7 and is referenced as 'Type of Store'. In addition, each shop is assigned with an attribute named 'Store Total Sales Area' which indicates the size of the retail store (see table 7). To gain knowledge of a customer preference over a particular shop the TLOG data had to be combined with the Stores Data Set (see figure 2). In addition, to retain more accurate results only the last year was considered from the TLOG Data Set, since customers might have changed their location and/or habits. The methodology which progressed to solve this feature extraction was to create a data frame, where for each customer it contained values of the type of shop visited and the average metrics of the value of the Store's Total Sales Area. Subsequently, the remaining chronologically TLOG Data was traversed to populate the Data Frame. Then, the values were standardized and fitted to the final tabular Data.

6.2.2.6 Visiting store at peak times The scope of this feature is to determine whether Customer's habit of purchasing something new is affected by the shop's fullness with customers. The hypothesis to back up this methodology lies in the fact that customers might be more prone to discover and purchase new products if they have the comfort in the shop to do so. The methodology was based on the provided customers, who are a targeted sample. Thus, this feature extraction technique includes a bias in the final result. The feature extraction technique was divided into two conceptual sections. The first involves the recording of each store's number of customers in a time-line via the package R package lubirdate [42]. This time-line was a null vector for each store which had the capacity to store each day and hour of the TLOG data with the number of customers. To populate these vectors the whole TLOG data was traversed and updated incrementally the vectors whether a customer's transaction was made during that hour. The second section, involves the measurement of each Customer participation in these stores in that time-line.

Hence, a value could be extracted to view whether they mostly participated in high or low peak hours for their shopping. The implementation of that was done via traversing again the TLOG data and measuring the average capacity Store's when the customer made her transaction. Finally, the values were standardized and fitted into the tabular Data Set.

6.2.2.7 Relative product Ratios The following feature extraction technique is divided upon two domains the Relative product Ratios of similar products and the ratio of the product of interest in the small period of time that was launch. Firstly, it will be analysed the similar products and then the specific product.

The product of interest is of a specific brand and category, thus it would be considered informative if measurements were taken to discover whether a customer was fan of this specific brand or item category. To give solution to that hypothesis the first step was to discover which other products were of the same brand and/or category. To accomplish that Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques were used on the 'Item Description' Attribute (can be found on Appendix table 8) to match other products with the same brand or the same use. Once the similar products were found using the plyr [32] package, recordings were taken of the number of purchases a customer had on these products explicitly (same brand or same category). Moreover, to emphasize on more recent transactions these recordings were taken for the whole length of the TLOG Data, then the last year, then the last 6 months and finally the last two months. For the product of interest there are limited purchases because it was just launched in the market. Hence the same methodology was applied for the feature extraction technique, measuring the number of purchases for the specific product. However, no time frames were measured due to the low amount of purchases. Ultimately, these values were standardized and inserted into the tabular Data.

6.3 Open Data Merging

6.3.1 Introduction

Open data were used in this research to enhance the classifiers accuracy. The key feature which allowed the Open Data merging was the Postcode provided by the

customers (see in the Appendix table 6). The purpose and the scope of munging (combining) the Open Data is stated on the chapter of Company's objectives where it is stated that Open Data should be made of use to test their significance. In addition, as stated in the Related Studies chapter that Demographic data have been used to estimate the customer's profile. Subsequently, a claim can be made that more accurate predictions can be made on customer's buying habits if we have more information about their background. Thus, acknowledging these two factors an Open Data investigation was commenced in order to find the most suitable Open Data to be merged with the customer's instances and give better predictions.

6.3.2 What is Open Data

At this point, it is ought to be explained what exactly is Open Data and which of these are used and how in this study. According to the journal Government Information Quarterly (2015) [43] "Open" must certify eleven definitions ⁹. The main identification of Openness are the free use, reuse and redistribution of data by confirming the appropriate citations. In addition as stated from the same journal [43] "Open data should not discriminate any person and must not restrict the use of the data to a specific field or venture." To conclude, according to the Proceedings of the 2013 IEEE 37th Annual conference [44] Open Data only refers to data that is available free of charge for the general public without any limitations.

The distributors of Open Data may vary. The most noticeable distributors in the Data Science field are the Open Linked Data and the Open Government Data. The former one, is defined as the process of following a set of best practices for publishing and connecting structured data on the Web [45]. The latter one, which is of the particular study's interest, is simply Government-related Data that have been made Open to the public [46].

Government Open Data is not a new thing according to this technical report by Hervais Simo Fhom (2015) [47], it is stated that about the last 10 years several governments have kick-started initiatives to publicize large sets of public data, incl. census data, crime statistics, traffic statistics, meteorological data, and health care data. The move aims at promoting transparency and government accountability,

⁹OpenDefinition

and achieving efficiency and effectiveness in Government. However, this is not the only goal, as stated on the above report [47] and fortified by the British government [48]. The second aim is to provide helpful data to private and commercial entities which will drive innovations and create a new wave of economic growth. Is thought provoking the fact that Open Government Data can uncover new insights. Some of the studies which exploit Government Open Data to its full potential are the use of Open data for anomaly detection in maritime surveillance where Open Data from many Governments were merged together [49], the influence of the PSI (Private sector involvement) directive on open government data [50] and even to predict war [51].

6.3.3 Open Data in this Case Study

In this study Open Government Data was used due to its content which lies mostly on Demographic and Census Data. The key characteristic for merging Open Data was the approximate postcode of the Customers (see table 6). As seen in the Customer's Data set (table 6) , the customer's profiling includes the postcode and the age. A feature to be capable used as a key for Open Data ingestion should be a noticeable identification. The postcode can provide accurate estimates due to its high cardinality whereas age would be misleading. Perhaps, combining postcode and age would be of consideration, however, current Open Data methodologies focus on regions and only very few studies involve both and are only age estimations per region. Thus age was not considered in this study, only the provided postcodes.

In this case study, the Customer Postcodes for privacy reasons do not contain the full length of their code. Moreover, the Postcodes were not of a fixed length, some of them were inaccurate and some of them did not respect the UK Postcode Formatting. In addition, the Open Data used in this study do not attribute their instances based on the Postal Code Area but on the Geography codes instead. Thus, in order to translate the Postcodes into the Geography codes the appropriate look-up tables should be found.

6.3.3.1 Geography Codes Prior heading to the Open Data analysis, firstly should be documented the Geography Codes. The 2011 Geography Codes are cre-

ated by the Office for National Statistics (ONS), the ones that were used in this study were the Output Areas (OA), the Lower Layer Super Output Area (LSOA) and the Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA). The first one OA is the lower level of Geography Code, these are built from clusters of adjacent unit POSTCODES in the United Kingdom and are the base unit for Census data releases. Due to their smaller size, Output Areas allow for a finer resolution of data analysis. Next, the LSOA are built from groups of contiguous OAs and have been automatically generated to be as consistent in population size as possible, and typically contain from four to six Output Areas. The Minimum population is 1000 and the mean is 1500. There is a Lower Layer Super Output Area for each POSTCODE in England and Wales. A pseudo code is available for Scotland, Northern Ireland, Channel Islands and the Isle of Man. Finally, the MSOAs are built from groups of contiguous LSOAs. The minimum population is 5000 and the mean is 7200 ¹⁰.

6.3.3.2 Open Data → OAC The OAC stands for Output Area (OA) Classification; this Open Data Set [52] is an effort from the ONS and the University College London (UCL) to classify each OA. The 2011 OAC is a three-tiered hierarchical geodemographic classification of the UK built using only 2011 UK Census data at the Output Area / Small Area level. It consists of 8 Supergroups, 26 Groups and 76 Subgroups. In addition, the OAC refers only to England and Wales.

The OA Geography Code, the lowest level of the Geography code, can contain some Postcodes areas ,however, its not deterministic that a Postcode will belong to only one OA. The lookup-table to translate the OA of the OAC Data Set into Postcodes, was fetched from the ONS ¹¹. Moreover, in the OA lookup table the digit length of the matched Postcode to the OA varied. Also, as a reminder it should be notified that either the Postcode's length of the Customers are fixed and most of them are limited to 5 Postcode length. The implementation required a series of step:

1. Extract the Groups and the OA code from the OAC table. The 26 Groups were taken into account since most of the Customers had a 5 digit length

¹⁰Information about the Geography Codes can be found in the following links ons.gov.uk, nationalarchives.gov.uk and nhs.uk

¹¹The ONS link for the lookup table.

Postcode, thus could not be achieved a Subgroup granularity.

2. Join the OAC with the OA to Postcode Lookup-table. Thus the current table would have instances of a Group and a Postcode.
3. Keep the unique OA values and link them with the Postcode which wins by majority.
4. Separate the table into tables of Postcode length of 3,4 and 5.
5. Extract by using majority vote from bigger than 3 length Postcode tables (i.e. 4 & 5), the lowest possible unrecorded Postcodes. For instance, if in the table which has exclusively all the 4 length Postcodes, by disregarding the last digit find the undocumented postcodes (i.e. the ones that are not in the table Postcode length 3).
6. For each customer depending on her provided Postcode length match it with the appropriate table length instance.

6.3.3.3 Geography Code Index Trees The rest Open Data were attributed either with a LSOA or a MSOA code. In addition, due to the large number of different Customer Postcodes and the immense number of LSOA and MSOA codes, engineering modifications had to be applied. The provided solution was given by using a series of steps and using the R packages 'data.table' [25], 'data.tree' [53] and 'treemap' [54]. The first step was to download and integrate the National Statistics Postcode Lookup UK (NSPL). This dataset contains the National Statistics Postcode Lookup (NSPL) for the United Kingdom. The NSPL relates current postcodes to a range of current statutory administrative, electoral, health and other statistical geographies via 'best-fit' allocation from the 2011 Census output areas. It supports the production of area based statistics from postcoded data. The NSPL is produced by ONS Geography, which provides geographic support to the Office for National Statistics (ONS) and geographic services used by other organisations¹². Next, the fields of interest of the lookup table (i.e. Postcode, MSOA and LSOA) were processed. Since, the Customer's Postcode provided was of a limited length, most likely

¹²Availabe in the data.gov.uk under the Open Government License (OGL).

having a 5 digit length, it was sensible for computational efficiency to allocate each 5 digit Postcode instead to an LSOA and MSOA code. The following procedures were applied to both LSOA and MSOA Geography Codes.

1. The first process was for each of the Geography Codes to allocate all the Postcodes under their domain.
2. For all the Postcodes of each Geography Code domain a modified Longest Common Substring algorithm was implemented to find the exact Postcode level that the Geography code referred to. For instance if all the Postcodes referred to a MSOA code have all their first 4 digits the same. This 4 digit Postcode will be referred to the MSOA code instead. If the algorithm resulted into less than a 4 digit Postcode then all the different first 5 digit sub Postcodes were referenced to the Geography Code.
3. From the Output of the above procedures two index Geography Codes were created one for the LSOA and one for the MSOA. In these index trees, each Geography Code was linked to a Postcode. An example can be viewed on figure 6.

```
> print(lookup.MSOA.post.tree$Navigate(path = "E/E1/E14"), "post", "MSOA", limit = 30)
LevelName post MSOA
1 E14
2 |--E14E
3 |   |--E14ER E14ER E02000870
4 |   |--E14EN E14EN E02000870
5 |   |--E14EA E14EA E02000870
6 |   |--E14ES E14ES E02000870
7 |   |--E14EQ E14EQ E02000870
8 |   |--E14EP E14EP E02000870
9 |   |--E14EB E14EB E02000870
10 |   |--E14ED E14ED E02000870
11 |   |--E14EW E14EW E02000870
12 |   |--E14ET E14ET E02000870
13 |   |--E14EJ E14EJ E02000870
14 |   |--E14EF E14EF E02000870
15 |   |--E14EE E14EE E02000870
16 |   |--E14EH E14EH E02000870
17 |   |--E14EL E14EL E02000870
18 |   |--E14EX E14EX E02000870
19 |   |--E14EG E14EG E02000873
20 |   |--E14EU E14EU E02000873
21 |   °--E14EY E14EY E02000879
22 |--E14B
23 |   |--E14BP E14BP E02000870
24 |   |--E14BX E14BX E02000870
25 |   |--E14BT E14BT E02000870
26 |   |--E14BS E14BS E02000870
27 |   |--E14BZ E14BZ E02000873
28 |   |--E14BL E14BL E02000873
29 |   |--E14BW E14BW E02000873
30 |   °--... 9 nodes w/ 0 sub
31 °--... 25 nodes w/ 374 sub
> |
```

Figure 6: A part of the MSOA index tree where for a Postcode part (E14), can be seen all its subdivisions Postcodes linked to a MSOA code.

4. For each Customer in the provided Data Set (figure 2), a procedure was implemented to provide the best possible match of her Postcode to a Geography Code. This was done, by either finding the specific Geography Code or if failed, assign to the MSOA code with the largest majority on the Postcode's Prefix on the Index Geography tree.

Following these procedures and using the ability of the index tree, it was computational possible and efficient to translate each customer's Postcode to a LSOA and MSOA code. This provided the capability of joining the rest of the Open Data described.

6.3.3.4 Open Data → IUC The Open Data IUC stands for Internet User Classification. This Geodemographic classification maps the geography of digital consumers within England by combining over seventy measures selected from survey and lifestyle data, alongside census and infrastructure performance statistics. This project forms an output of an ESRC funded PhD and research project, both undertaken at the University of Liverpool. This project aims to assist the targeted marketing applications, policy delivery and strategic planning, where Internet use and engagement characteristics of a target population are of high importance. The Internet User Classification (IUC) has a two-tier structure comprising four Super-groups and eleven Groups that are used to classify all Lower Layer Super Output (LSOA) areas in England [55]. The procedure with this Open Data was straightforward, since the Data provided only categorical variables it were joined with the customers via the LSOA code.

6.3.3.5 Open Data → Dwelling Age Group Counts This Data Set is provided by the Valuation Office Agency (VOA) [56]. The counts are calculated from domestic property data for England and Wales extracted from the VOA administrative database on 31 March 2015. Data on property types and number of bedrooms have been used to form property categories by which to view the data and data on build period has been used to create property build period categories. The Data Set has attributed each LSOA Geography Code with the count of houses to each 10 year period from prior to 1900 until to 2015. Moreover, are calculated on the Data Set the two 10 year periods with the most houses on each LSOA district and the

percentage they occupy from all the age periods. The transformation implemented in this Data Set was to attribute each customer with the 10 year period with the most counts in her LSOA area and provide the percentage that this period occupied from all the other age periods. Consequently, there were created 12 attributes for the 10 year Age Periods and each attribute was either zero to each customer or contained the percentage if the specific Age Period was dominant in the customer's LSOA code. Moreover, the values were normalised before inserted into the tabular Data.

6.3.3.6 Open Data → Median House Prices The Median House Prices Open Data were provided by the ONS [56] and specifies the median price of each household quarterly from 2014 Q2 until 2015 Q2 for each MSOA code in England and Wales. In addition the number of house sales were provided for the last Quarter. The transformation this Data Set was subjected to, was to select the last Quarter of median house Price for each MSOA code, along with the number of sales in the last Quarter and the ratio of change in the median house price between the 2014 Q2 to 2015 Q2 for each MSOA code. Finally, the resulted attributes after joining with the customer's MSOA code were normalised and fitted into the tabular Data Set.

6.3.3.7 Open Data → Population Weighted Centroids The aim of this Open Data is to provide for each LSOA code the center of the Population in that District in order to have a good Geo Spatial representation of where each Customer is located. The methodology was implemented by the ONS ¹³; which used the median algorithm Median Center (sic) function in ArcGIS 10.0 ¹⁴, with parameters the coordinates and the populations of each household in each LSOA code. Where the calculated centroid fell outside the boundary of the area being calculated, or within two metres of the area boundary, it was moved to the nearest location at least two metres inside the area boundary. An illustration of the algorithm can be viewed in figure 7.

¹³The actual Data Set was gathered from the Consumer Data Research Center. on October 24, 2016

¹⁴The median center algorithm provided by the ArcGIS Resource Center.

Figure 7: An illustration of the Median Center algorithm provided by the ArcGIS Resource Center.

The Data Set contains the centroids of each LSOA code in England, Wales and Scotland.

Hence, the copyrights fall under the National Statistics data, the Scottish Government data and the Ordnance Survey data ©Crown copyright and database right 2015. The funding was provided by the Economic and Social Research Council ES/L011840/1.

The specific Data Set, contains each LSOA code with the X (Easting) any Y (Northing) values ¹⁵ of the Median Center algorithm output. Moreover, each LSOA code is attributed with the Total Population, the Household Population and the Number of Households. All measurements are referring to the year 2011. The three latter variables referring to Populations were normalised and then the Data Set was joined with the tabular Data via the LSOA code.

6.3.3.8 Open Data → Car or Van Availability The Open Data Set Car or Van Availability specifies the number of cars and Vans in each LSOA district. The use of this Data Set was considered to satisfy the hypothesis that Customer's with more travelling convenience or wealth would alternate their buying patterns. The Data Set was downloaded from the the Nomis ¹⁶ service. *The Nomis service is provided by the ONS to provide free access to the most detailed and up-to-date UK labour market statistics from official sources. Moreover, is documented that Under the terms of the Open Government Licence (OGL) and UK Government Licensing*

¹⁵The terms Easting and Northing are geographic Cartesian coordinates for a point. Easting refers to the eastward-measured distance (or the x-coordinate), while Northing refers to the northward-measured distance (or the y-coordinate).

¹⁶The Open Data was retrieved from Nomis on October 24,2016.

Framework (launched 30 September 2010), anyone wishing to use or re-use ONS material, whether commercially or privately, may do so freely without a specific application for a licence, subject to the conditions of the OGL and the Framework.. In specific, the Data Set contained the for each LSOA code in England, Wales and Scotland the number of cars or vans that are owned, or available for use, by one or more members of a household. This includes company cars and vans that are available for private use. It does not include motorbikes or scooters, or any cars or vans belonging to visitors. The count of cars or vans in an area relates only to households. Cars or vans used by residents of communal establishments are not counted. Households with 10 to 20 cars or vans are counted as having only 10. Responses indicating a number of cars or vans greater than 20 were treated as invalid and a value was imputed. The transformation approached to this Data Set was to normalise each count of cars per household and then fit it on the tabular Data Set.

6.3.3.9 Open Data → Female Economic Activity This table provides information that classifies Female residents aged 16 to 74 by economic activity at each LSOA code, for the United Kingdom as at census day, 27 March 2011. It also provides additional information about the unemployed population (including full-time students), with estimates of the number of long-term unemployed, those who have never worked, and the classification of unemployed by key age groups. This Data Set was regarded due to the fact that in the Exploratory Analysis subsection 6.2.1 the significant amount of Customer's have noted their gender as female, which is why a more detailed focus on Economic Activity was given to the female population. This Open Data Set was provided by the Nomis Service ¹⁷ of ONS. The procedure implemented for this Data was to disregard some Aggregated Summary metrics and Normalise the rest which would sum up to the whole Female population of the LSOA district and then insert in to the tabular Data Set.

6.3.3.10 Open Data → Living Arrangements This Open Data Set provides information that classifies residents aged 16 and over in households by their living arrangements, for United Kingdom as at census day, 27 March 2011. The living

¹⁷The Open Data was retrieved from Nomis on October 24, 2016.

arrangements classification differs from marital and civil partnership status because cohabiting takes priority over other categories. For example, if a person is divorced and cohabiting, then in results for living arrangements they are classified as cohabiting. The Data Set is attributed with the LSOA code and was gathered by the Nomis¹⁸ service of ONS. In addition, it was specified by the Nomis service that in order to protect against disclosure of personal information from the 2011 Census, there has been swapping of records in the Census database between different geographic areas, and so some counts will be affected. In the main, the greatest effects will be at the lowest geographies, since the record swapping is targeted towards those households with unusual characteristics in small areas. The Data transformation regarding this Data Set was to disregard some Aggregated Summary metrics and Normalise the rest and then insert them into the tabular Data Set.

6.3.3.11 Open Data → Female Occupation The Female Occupation Open Data provides information that classifies Female residents aged 16 to 74 in employment the week before the census by occupation, for United Kingdom on LSOA code as at census day, 27 March 2011. Classes of the Occupation include Managers, Professional occupations, Administrative, Caring, Sales and others. The Data was assembled from the Nomis¹⁹ Service by the ONS. Beyond that a disclaimer from the Nomis service states that to protect against disclosure of personal information from the 2011 Census, there has been swapping of records in the Census database between different geographic areas, and so some counts will be affected. In the main, the greatest effects will be at the lowest geographies, since the record swapping is targeted towards those households with unusual characteristics in small areas. The procedure undertaken to allocate the Female Occupation on the Tabular Data was to just Normalise each attribute before joining with the Customers on the Tabular Data via the LSOA code.

¹⁸The Open Data was retrieved from Nomis on October 24, 2016.

¹⁹The Open Data was retrieved from Nomis on October 24, 2016.

6.4 TLOG and Open Data

6.4.0.1 Distance to shop metrics The last feature was created by combining the TLOG data and the Population Weighted Centroids Open Data (see paragraph 6.3.3.7). This feature investigates if the average distance between a Customer and a shop have any significance. To accomplish this, the last approximate year of the TLOG data was considered due to the computational efficiency and to have better estimates by having sufficient data for the customers. The procedure involved to traversing the TLOG data in one pass and calculating the euclidean distance between the Shop and the customer for each instance. In order to accomplish that the Coordinates of each Customer and Shop were calculated using the Population Weighted Centroids Open Data. Subsequently, traversing the TLOG data the mean and variance of the distance for each Customer to a shop were calculated using an online algorithm, to ensure a one pass over the TLOG data. Finally, the output variables mean and variance of each Customer to the shop were normalised and inserted into the tabular Data.

6.5 Data Cleaning

After merging all the available Data it was needed to adjust the Tabular Data in order to have the best outcomes. It was noticed that due to combining multiple resources many of the variables were highly correlated, hence an effort was given to remove the appropriate. Moreover, the since the Open Data was derived from different sources would not always cover the complete geographic area of the customers, hence missing values methodologies had to be imputed. Moreover, as detected from the variables extracted in order to maintain same distances the Open Data were normalised from 0 to 1 and the rest of the Data which included customer behaviour were scaled using z - standardization from 0 to approximately 1. The latter one was done due to the fact that the customers had major inequalities, thus normalising them would bias the prediction accuracy and distance metrics.

6.5.0.1 Correlation Test - Feature Removal The first step was to transform all the categorical variables in to Dummy Variables. A dummy variable takes the

value 0 or 1 to indicate the absence or presence of some categorical effect that may be expected. Thus if a Categorical Feature has 6 classes this will be interpreted with 5 Dummy Variables one for each one of them and the default state which can be the first class. Transforming, the categorical Variables into Dummy Variables make them applicable for testing and useful in more Classification algorithms. The step following involved producing correlation similarity matrices between the extracted features. The Pearson's correlation metric was used to produce these matrices. Three matrices were produced depending on the family of attributes. The first involved the features which were extracted from Data sources excluding the Open Data. The second one involved the attributes where Open Data were combined to produce, but without the categorical Variables (Dummy Variables) and the last matrix involved the categorical Variables exclusively. The reason to produce three matrices instead of one with all the variables was for computational efficiency and for better handling the variables whatsoever there was no loss of information since the sources of the three different similarity matrices varied.

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient produces an estimate of correlation between two features from -1 to 1 which indicates from highly negative correlation to highly positive correlation accordingly. In this case study, an absolute threshold of 0.8 was set to distinguish the highly correlated measures. As expected, from the first matrix involving the TLOG Data the measures the Ratio features refereed in paragraph 6.2.2.7 had the highest degree of correlation, between these features the biggest value was 0.86 however they were not removed since they might still provide information depending on customer's change of ratio. Following, from the Open Data matrix it was discovered that some features were correlated above a 0.9 threshold. These features involved describing total amounts. For instance the total amount of people, cars or properties in an area, these attributes were deprecated with a care-full manner. It was lucid to remove attributes without loss of any possible information hence this involved removing the attributes which were high correlated with more than one other features and make sure that the rest would not be correlated over the 0.8 threshold. Lastly, from the matrix of the categorical variables no high correlations were established.

6.5.0.2 Missing Data Moreover, some values were missing in the Data Set. Two tactics were introduced to face the missing values. In the first place the categorical variables found in the Open Data were removed by only taking into consideration the rest classes when transformed into Dummy variables. The second tactic in was to replace the non available numeric values with the mean of that feature.

7 Supervised Learning Methodology

7.1 Introductory

7.1.1 Sampling

The Data Set of the study is remarkably unbalanced hence Sampling techniques were introduced to favour the minority class. Two main categories exist in the literature about re-sampling the data Set as to offset this imbalance. The first one is the Under-Sampling were instances of the majority class are dismissed and the second one is the Over-Sampling were bootstrapping techniques are applied to produce more instances in the minority class. These methodologies can be used separately, combined or use ensemble methodologies. In this paper the Under-Sampling and the Over-Sampling methodologies will be analysed. The algorithms used for this study derived from [57].

7.1.1.1 Under-Sampling Two Under-Sampling strategies were involved in this study. The former one which can be regarded as the Naive one is the random Under Sampling were a seed for randomness is generated and a ratio to establish the desirable ratio between the majority and the minority class; then the appropriate instances are removed. The other strategy used, resides in the neighboring methodology. In specific, one of them, the neighborhood cleaning rule (NCL) [58] which fits the whole Data Set in Neighborhoods (Clusters) based on a scalar provided. Then for each Neighborhood if the the instance is of the majority class will have a possibility of being removed ²⁰. This methodology has been viewed as having better

²⁰The documentation regarding the code can be accessed in scikit-learn.org, retrieved on 01-10-2016.

results than implementing Random Under Sampling [58].

7.1.1.2 Over-Sampling The Over-Sampling methods as stated, over populates the Data Set with similar instances of the minority class in order for the Classifier to be more tolerant towards this class. The most popular algorithm regarding the Over-Sampling is SMOTE(Synthetic Minority Oversampling TEchnique). This procedure takes into account a number of neighboring instances each time in the minority class and produces a new instance based on these neighboring instance attributes [59]. Moreover, an enhancement to this procedure has been made issued as Borderline over-sampling [60] which tends to populate more the instances which attributes are more closely related to the opponent class; thus it is claimed to achieve better predictions in some cases than SMOTE. In addition, in this study it was experimented the Random-Oversampling; which is the action of bootstrapping the minority class with replacement.

7.1.2 Classification Algorithms

A set of Classification algorithms were considered in this study. These are divided into two main families the Bayes and the Ensemble with Decision Trees. The choice of having a repertoire of Classification algorithms from two different families enhances the attained knowledge from the Data Set. Moreover, in both of these families there are algorithms which are more tolerant to many attributes. This was done in order to certify the significance of the attributes.

7.1.2.1 Bayes Classifiers

Naive Bayes

The first classifier, which is defined by its simplicity, was the Naive Bayes Classifier; it is based on the Bayes Theorem. The algorithm used for this study was from the Weka Data Mining Software [61]. The specific algorithm suits this case study because handles continuous data by using statistical methods for nonparametric density estimation (kernel density estimation) [62]. This conforms to this case study since not all of the attributes necessarily follow a Gaussian model (Normal Distribution).

Bayes Net

The other classifier of the Bayes family was the Bayes Net. As it is widely known, the Naive Bayes is a subcategory of the Bayes Network algorithms. The difference between the Naive Bayes and the other Bayes Net algorithms is that the Naive Bayes model assumes that all the attributes are conditionally independent; whereas the rest of the Bayes Net algorithm family by exploiting the conditional independence using usually heuristic search algorithms and estimators may possibly achieve better predictions from this joint probability distribution. Hence, the Bayes Net model could uncover some dependencies among the attributes and possibly achieve better results and infer knowledge from the attributes. The type of Bayes Net algorithm used for this study was retrieved from Weka [61].

7.1.2.2 Ensemble Learning with Decision Trees Classifiers

Introductory

Two topics ought to be covered in this section the Decision Trees and the Ensemble Learning. To begin with, Ensemble Learning is being investigated by the Machine Learning (ML) community due to its capabilities of combining Classifiers in order to make better estimates. In this study, the focus had been kept in decision trees and Ensemble Learning. This combination had been proven to stack remarkably well, in view of the fact that in general terms Decision Trees are computationally scalable, handle missing values, are robust to outliers, do not require feature scaling and can handle both numeric and categorical variables. However, Decision Trees are known that can be prone to variance or bias sometimes, thus, by using Ensemble Learning methodologies these traits can be diminished. It is remarkable the fact that Ensemble Learning and Decision Trees can be comparable to some of the top ML algorithms (ANN) [63] and used in ML competitions, such as kaggle. *In addition to this claim it was stated by the sponsoring company to investigate Ensemble Learning methodologies.* The Ensemble Learning methodologies that were covered in this study include the Classification Algorithms Random Forest, Rotation Forest and Regularized Gradient Boosting.

Random Forest

The Random Forest Ensemble Methodology depends on a combination of Decision Trees Predictors; each Tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently (Bagging) and with the same distribution for all trees in the forest

[64]. This methodology can be regarded as a Boosting Methodology since each Decision Tree's outcome on the predicted value, are voted in between to provide the final estimate. The algorithm used for this Classification Algorithm was provided by Weka [61].

Rotation Forest

The Rotation Forest methodology lies in producing many base classifiers like Random Forest but by sub-sampling the features of the Data Set and transforming them via Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and re-training them [65]. The Rotation Forest procedure was used via Weka's [61] software.

Regularized Gradient Boosting

The pattern used in the modified version of Gradient Boosting in this case study takes as well into consideration a set of Trees. Moreover, the Gradient Boosting principle stands in its knowledge of Gradient Descent where each Decision Tree learns at each step based on a parameter. In addition, the regularization is the state were keeping fit the parameters for the next Decision Tree classifier to learn. The version of Gradient Boosting used in this is the XGBoost [66].

7.1.3 Evaluation Criteria

A careful notice should be made in what kind of Evaluation Criteria were used in this study since the Data Set was vastly skewed. The first Evaluation Criterion considered between the Classifiers was the Area Under the Curve (AUC). The AUC measures the area under the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve of a Classifier; the ROC curve is plot of the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR). The AUC measurement was selected since it is not biased by the class imbalance as the accuracy would have been. Moreover, the Recall and the Precision measurements were taken into account in order to distinguish in the minority class how many instances were labeled correctly. However, the main evaluation metric was the AUC measurement since the main consideration was to target the correct customers building a robust model.

7.2 Methodology and Results

This section provides an overview of the Supervised Learning methodology applied to this research. The methodology was divided into five conceptual phases which are detailed and documented following. These phases cover the study from the initial point of the feature exploration procedures to the conclusive end of the study regarding the imbalance Data Set.

7.2.1 Feature Evaluation

The first step regarding the Supervised Methodology for attribute selection was to use a set of (Linear) Regressions. Two forms of Regressions were used to test the significance of each attribute. In the first place the logistic regression was used. Then, as some studies suggest [67], [68] for highly unbalanced Data to use the Lasso (least absolute shrinkage and selection operator) Regression and in specific the Binomial Lasso [69], for this case study.

For the Logistic Regression a step function was used on the Tabular Data which had as parameters in both directions and the AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) score. The both step function works by comparing the AIC improvements from dropping each candidate variable, and adding each candidate variable between the upper and lower bound regressor sets supplied, from the current model, and by dropping or adding the one variable that leads to the best AIC improvement (the smallest AIC). Implementing this methodology it maintained all the attributes but regarded only a few of high significance, these were some of the most significant with a score lower than 0.01 of significance.

1. The Age of the Customer (see figure 2).
2. The Shop Interval (see paragraph 6.2.2.2).
3. One of the Ratio features (see paragraph 6.2.2.7).
4. Both the Graph Extracted Features (see paragraph 6.2.2.3).
5. The Shop Probability (see paragraph 6.2.2.4).

Following the Lasso Regression was tested on a Cross Validation testing and by setting the parameter λ to give the minimum mean cross-validated error, the only significant were two attributes regarding the customer's Ratio Features (see paragraph 6.2.2.7). Implementing these regressions gave an insight about the Feature Importance, however, in the pages covered all the attributes were taken into account to uncover possible relationships in between.

7.2.2 Supervised Methodology Comparison

In this phase it was vital to asses the different Classification algorithms in order to process to next phase of the Supervised Attribute Selection and determine which is the best Supervised Learning approach. Hence, it was tested with all the attributes on every Classification algorithm covered. The process involved splitting the Tabular Data in a Stratified Sample of a 70% training Set and a 30% Test Set. Moreover, due to the fact that the Data Set was highly skewed were the minority class instances assembled a 2% of all the instances a Sampling (see subsection 7.1.1) approach was introduced. It was noticed that by taking major steps of re-balancing the training Data via Sampling biased the outputs, as noticed by the evaluation Criteria. Hence, at this stage the Sampling method used was regarded as conservative. This is due to the fact that only the Under-Sampling approach was used in this phase. In detail, the NCL procedure was implemented in the training Set and the end result would state the minority class having almost 5% instances in the population of the Data Set.

The algorithms tested during this procedure were processed with their default hyper-parameters and/or tuned trivially based on an iterative process. Since, in this stage the aim was to asses externally the Classifiers no major involvement with hyper-parameter was done. The scores from the output of each Classifier can be seen on the table 1.

Table 1: The Evaluation Criteria of the Classifiers (expressed in percentages).

Classifiers	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC
NaiveBayes	85	5	35	66
BayesNet	86	5	36	70
RandomForest	98	100*	0.3	66
RotationForest	97	11	1.5	64
XGBoost	97	21	0.8	69

The estimates of the table take into account the minority class metrics, in which we are interested. Analysing the table the first point of interest is the Recall measure meaning how many instances of the minority class were labeled correctly. In which the Bayes models win. Moreover, having as a metric the AUC it can be seen that the BayesNet and the XGBoost have the highest, however, they have a big difference in the accuracy. Henceforth, the XGBoost Classification algorithm was used in the sections following.

* *There were no (0) False Positive (Majority class) hence it was divided by 1.*

7.2.3 Parameter Tuning

The Regularized Gradient Boosting was analysed to provide information on which are the features to consider in the Supervised Learning scheme. The first thing that was considered was to tune the Hyper-parameters via Grid Search by using the [57]. This methodology tests the combination of each hyper-parameter and outputs the best based on the evaluation criterion, which is the AUC. To have the best results the Grid Search was carried out using an 8-fold cross validation on the 70% training data. Main considerations in the tuning methodology was the sub-sampling of attributes meaning that each tree would regard different set of attributes and also this applied in every level of the tree. Other considerations taken into account were the learning rate that the Gradient Boosting algorithm should have, the max-depth of the trees and other regularization parameters. Furthermore, the early stop functionality was tested to when the model reached its highest possible AUC metric and stop there. This was tested due to the fact that is noticed that when a model reaches its final peak on an evaluation metric tends to over-fit in the

consecutive steps. Finally, it was noticed that when using multiple trees (Boosting), the Gradient Boosting methodology would consider each starting tree separately and then by combining their results (Boosting) it was seen that it improved the AUC and accuracy scores.

Moreover, in order for the XGBoost model to regard the minority class more considerately, some additional tuning took place. The first step was to re-weight the instances, assigning more weight to the minority class, however, although this process was tested with different set of weights the implementation caused degrade drastically the performance of the model each time. Next, the available hyper-parameter to tune was the max delta step which is responsible in to favour the minority class by constraining each tree's weight estimation [66], however, trying different values the performance would remain the same. The last parameter to experiment was the scale of the weight between the two classes that weights more the targeted class based on a given ratio when the Decision Tress are constructed. The results documented by alternating this hyper-parameter decreased the prediction metrics. Thus, the findings regarding he imbalance hyper-parameter tuning in this stage, were considered unsuccessful.

7.2.4 Supervised Attribute Selection

The two most well known methods in the ML community on Attribute Selection via Supervised Learning is the Backward and Forward Selection. The former one, involves starting with all the features, testing the deletion of each feature using a chosen model evaluation criterion, deleting the feature (if any) that improves the model the most by being deleted, and repeating this process until no further improvement is possible. The latter one, involves starting with no features in the model, testing the addition of each features using a chosen model evaluation criterion, adding the features (if any) that improves the model the most, and repeating this process until none improves the model. A trained XGBoost model automatically calculates feature importance on the predictive modeling problem, hence in this use case the Backward Selection process was chosen. Three different procedures were involved in order to Cross Validated the findings. The first one (Fscore) involved ranking the attributes based on the XGBoost's variable importance function which ranks each

attribute on how many time the specific attribute was split in the Decision Tree(s). The second one (Gain), takes relative contribution of the corresponding attribute to the model calculated by taking each attribute’s contribution for each Decision Tree in the model. A higher value of this metric when compared to another feature implies it is more important for generating the prediction. The last one was based on the Somer’s D index. This index measures the ordinal association between two possibly dependent variables, in addition this index is non parametric [70]. In this case it was examined each feature versus the outcome. The algorithm was retrieved from [71].

Reproducing the procedures what stands out is that the correlation (using Pearson’s method) between the important (FScore) variables regarded from the XGBoost model had only a 9% correlation variable importance with the Somer’s D index. The other feature ranking based on the model were relatively similar.

Figure 8: The histogram of the Fscore Attribute Evaluation using XGBoost and the histogram of the Somer’s D methodology. It can be seen that both principles regard only few features to be important and the rest chunk of attributes is labeled as non of a great importance. (Large values on the x-axis interpret a great significance.)

To asses the prediction performance of each Attribute Selection methodology in this phase; from the tabular Data after making the appropriate corrections (see subsection 6.5), each of these three models was tested its AUC accuracy over an 8-fold Cross Validation in the same 70% training Set. The hyper-parameters were defined from subsection 7.2.3 and an equivalent mild NCL UnderSampling was configured as in subsection 7.2.2 ²¹, moreover 100 Decision Trees were set to be

²¹A careful notice, that since the attributes were different, the Under-Sampling due to its Neighboring property behaved differently removing a slightly different amount of instances in the ma-

trained in parallel and combine their predictions. Lastly, the procedure was tuned with an early stop in the learning procedure to avoid possible over-fitting. Below in table 2 can be seen the output performances were the AUC configurations are the mean and standard Deviation of the test-set of each of the 8 - folds. Moreover, the rest of the predictions took into consideration the whole training Data of 70% against the test set of the tabular Data. Thus in the next step the AUC values will be taken into consideration.

Table 2: The Evaluation Criteria of the various Attribute Selection models (expressed in percentages).

AttrSelection	N.of.Attr	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	AUC-mean	AUC-std
Fscore	62	97	6	1.3	88	2.7
Gain	49	97	10	1.6	87	1.8
Somer's D	25	97	13	9	81	1.2

The table 2 illustrates the performance of each methodology. Recongnising the results there is not a clear winner, however, the "Gain" methodology seems the most appealing due to the fact that maintains a high score average of AUC and the standard deviation is considerably lower than the "Fscore" procedure.

7.2.5 Imbalance

In the previous phase it was found which is the best model to make predictions, however, since the company wants to attract the minority group (i.e. the potential customers) it is vital in this subsection to explore methodologies that could favour the minority class. The first step involved tuning the hyper-parameters responsible for balancing the output, however, as previously documented the results were not encouraging, the left configurations were left the same as the previous phase. The only solution was to experiment with different Sampling techniques. The model Somer's D was selected in this phase due to the fact that performed in every experiment higher scores in the Precision and Recall metrics (see table 2). The procedure in this stage experimenting and combinig different Sampling techniques. To start with, the two under-sampling techniques (see subsection 7.1.1) were compared

minority class.

and it was not noticed that the NCL performed better when alone. Below on table 3 can be seen the output of the various radius in the neighborhood parameter of the NCL. The table demonstrates the various metrics when using a stratified sample of 70% training Set and an 30% test set ²². The AUC measure was not taken into account since it relatively behaved the same because it was provided in the model to use this metric as the Evaluation Criterion.

Table 3: The Evaluation Criteria of the NCL different size of Neighborhoods. (expressed in percentages).

Neighb.Size	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
40	97	13	9
70	95	10	18
100	91	7	31
120	87	6	39
150	79	5	52

As can be seen from the table as the Neighborhood size increases, meaning that more samples being removed from the majority class leads the Accuracy to decrease exponentially. Consecutive, the testing of the Over-Sampling technique took over. It was documented that the Random Over-Sampling subsection 7.1.1 managed to achieve the best predictions. In the next table 4 can be viewed the different metrics when alternating the ratio ²³ between the majority class and the minority class.

Table 4: The Evaluation Criteria of the Random OverSampling regulated with different Ratios (expressed in percentages).

ratio	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
0.1	98	0	0
0.5	98	71	1
1	98	38	1

The Over-Sampling technique seem to have a very low Recall estimate which

²²The Evaluation Criteria are produced on account of the minority class.

²³The ratio is from 0 to 1 where 1 represents a perfect balance between the two classes.

translates that almost no Customer's will be labeled as interested for the new product. Even when combined with the NCL Under-Sampling procedure would deprived the scores in the Evaluation Criteria.

From the Sampling methodologies so far, including the hyper parameter tuning only the NCL procedure achieved to "fetch" potential customers. On the account of the importance to estimate a better Recall percentage including the accuracy measure new procedures were formulated. Previous research on Imbalance Ensemble Learning [72] has recognised great prediction performance on Imbalance Data when using Boosting methodologies. One of the best performances documented in that study involve using an AdaBoost Ensemble Classifier which is assembled from many weak Classifiers. Each of these Classifiers was trained with a sub-sample of the Data Set; each sub-sample was a product of a Random Under-Sampling (see subsection 7.1.1). Consequently, this approach was re-produced in this study by initialising 100 XGBoost models were each one of them was trained in a different Random-Under-sampled Data. Each Gradient Boosting model contained one tree from which the training progressed. The hyper-parameters of these models were tuned equivalently with the previous procedures. The table 5 illustrates the different evaluation metrics, the ratio expresses the Under Sampling ratio in a decreasing manner, a variable of 1 would mean a full balance.

Table 5: The Evaluation Criteria of the Random UnderSampling with different sub-samples regulated with different Ratios (expressed in percentages).

ratio	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
0.1	97	20	5
0.2	96	13	13
0.3	94	10	24
0.4	90	7	34
0.5	86	6	44
0.6	82	5	48

8 Discussion & Conclusion

8.1 Feature Extraction

Main purpose of this study was to evaluate which features were the most prominent and applicable to determine the potential customers. In order to view each XGBoost model's rank of the attributes the `xgbfi` tool²⁴. From using that tool, it can be seen that the Graph Mined feature (see paragraph 6.2.2.3) was always the first one to be considered by the metrics Gain and Fscore. Moreover, it always claimed the first place by having interactions with the variables of the Relative Product Ratios (see paragraph 6.2.2.7) and the Aggregated metrics (see paragraph 6.2.2.1). Consequently, the two later features were regarded of high importance in the XGBoost models respectively. Hence, considering the good performance the Graph Mined feature had, possibly more information can be ingested in the Bipartite Graph. A recommendation would be to add purchase properties between the edges like the usage of discounts used or include the time component. Moreover, there is abundant space for more research in the link Analysis algorithms.

Furthermore observations on the feature importance indicate a high importance on the Intermittent Time Series metric features. It can be distinguished using the `xgbfi` tool that these features tend to interact with the ones mentioned above (Graph Mined, Relative Product Ratios and Aggregated Metrics). Finally, analysing the importance of the Open Data it was discovered that the Open Data of Female Economic Activity (see paragraph 6.3.3.9) and Female Occupation (see paragraph 6.3.3.11) maintained a high score. This statement indicates that exist further associations between these Open Data and the rest, which can be useful in Marketing campaigns by using a Customer Profile.

8.2 Supervised Learning

Numeral outcomes stand out from the Supervised Learning methodology. The first key point that stands out is that it was difficult to achieve a high Recall measure without affecting the other Evaluation metrics. This is of greater importance

²⁴Retrieved from github, on the 6 of November of 2016.

since the company will have to set a certain threshold on balancing the Recall and the misclassified instances in order to approach the potential customers depending on the marketing budget. It was noticed throughout the phase of dealing with the imbalance, that only the Under-Sampling technique provided an adequate enough solution. Clearly, this has to do with the fact that the Data Set's distribution of the two outcomes are highly merged; thus only by letting increase the amount of False Positive Rate (majority class) can be achieved a higher Recall (True Potential Customers). Moreover, it is noticed that the Under-Sampling performs better when implemented "carefully". This states to the notion of either using the NCL technique or many Random-Under Sampled Data Sets for training, by training on one occurrence of Random-Under Sampled Data Set tends to bias the prediction.

The interesting part of the study which raise questions is that the Somer's D model was the most applicable to achieve a higher Recall. As was noticed from the Supervised Attribute Selection phase it had the least AUC measure albeit it was the most appropriate in order to achieve higher Recall measures. Two possible reasons appear to justify this phenomenon. The first might be that due to the fact that the Somer's D index promotes the association of each variable with the outcome, the second case might lie in the fact that because it has less Attributes it performs differently. To test the latter hypothesis from the 'Gain' model (see subsection 7.2.4) fewer attributes were selected. This resulted in to having lower AUC measures but the Recall was higher, similarly noticed in table 2 when comparing the 'Gain' methodology with the 'Somer's D'. Hence, this concludes that the XGBoost model is quite robust on the attribute Selection methodology. It perceived more attributes in order to gain higher AUC measures; whereas when selecting fewer attributes the AUC measure drops but they tend to perceive a higher Recall measure instead. Another noticeable aspect of the project is that having fewer attributes Sampling methods which rely on Neighboring methodologies tend to perform better, since the calculations of measuring distances become more reliable by having less dimensions. In addition the fact that models which incorporated Categorical Dummy Variables might had biased the NCL Neighborhood calculations.

More research can be done in building a customised objective function in the XGBoost model tuned in the company's specific strategies of the marketing cam-

paign. This approach could consider different penalization scores when building the Ensemble models in order to maintain an equilibrium between the Recall metric of the minority class and the False Positive metric (misclassified instances of the majority class).

8.3 Conclusion

Various methodologies took place in this study to address the issue of targeting customers for a new product over a targeted sample. It was shown that using Graph Mining procedures by using the Personalised Pagerank algorithm on the TLOG data can contribute vastly on the prediction efficiency. In addition, creating aggregated features and feature ratio indicators (for purchasing a specific genre of products) for each time period in the TLOG data was proven a good strategy. Moreover, the Intermittent Time Series metric features contributed accordingly enhancing the predictions. Finally, from the Open Data used in the study only two of them indicated to be contributing. In the Supervised Learning methodology the Regularized Gradient Boosting Classifier was concluded that provided the best results among the others used. Furthermore, its prediction efficiency was increased when using the customised hyper-parameters and using its Boosting methodology in multiple (parallel) Decision Trees. Moreover, it was derived that it was difficult to achieve a high Recall measure without increasing the amount of the misclassified instances, even by using various balancing methodologies, this fact assigned to the nature of the Data Set in the current study.

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9 Appendix

9.1 Tables

Table 6: Customers Attributes explanation and Data type

Customers	
Customer ID	Identification Code (int)
Gender	Gender (male, female, unknown) (String)
Age	Age based on supplied date of birth (float)
Approx. Postcode	Part of Postcode for privacy reasons (String)

Table 7: Stores Attributes explanation and Data type

Stores	
Store ID	Identification Code (int)
Store Name	Name of the Store (String)
Type of Store	Store Attribute (String)
SAG	Sales Area Group (String)
Store Total Sales Area	Retail sales area within the store (int)
Number of Floors	Number of floors in the store (int)
Postcode	The Store's Postcode (String)

Table 8: Products/Items Attributes explanation and Data type

Items	
Item ID	Unique ID for each product (int)
Item Description	Product Description (String)
Brand Description	Brand Description (String)
Sub Brand Description	Sub-brand Description (String) (Will be identical to brand description in some cases)
Item hierarchy Description_2	Product hierarchy Description level 2 (Highest) (String)
Item hierarchy Description_3	Product hierarchy Description level 3 (String)
Item hierarchy Description_4	Product hierarchy Description level 4 (String)
Item hierarchy Description_5	Product hierarchy Description level 5 (String)
Item hierarchy Description_6	Product hierarchy Description level 6 (Lowest) (String)

Table 9: TLOG Attributes explanation and Data type

TLOG	
Customer ID	Customer Identification Code (int)
Store ID	Store Identification Code (int)
Transaction ID	Transaction Identification Code (Big int)
Date of transaction	Date of transaction (Date/time)
Time of transaction	Time of transaction (Date/time)
Payment type	Payment type (i.e. Credit card, Cash etc) (String)
Item ID	Item Identification Code (int)
Number of Items	Number of units bought (int)
Paid amount	What the customer paid, including VAT (after discounts for any deals have been applied) (float)
Number of Items on deal	Units bought on a deal (int)
Deal reward money	Value of discount applied (float)
Deal reward points	Advantage Card points awarded as part of a deal (e.g. get 100 points when you buy this product) (float)

Table 10: Responses Attributes explanation and Data type

Responses	
Customer ID	Customer Identification Code (int)
Output	Binary 0/1 if she/he bought the product (int)

9.2 Figures

Figure 9: The histograms of the Item frequencies in the TLOG Data. The Data is divided in these two histograms, on the left are the top high occurrences and on the left are the rest of the occurrences. It can be seen that the Data follows the same pattern.

Figure 10: The histograms of the Customer frequencies in the TLOG Data.

Figure 11: The histograms of the Stores frequencies in the TLOG Data.